

Theoretical-Scientific and Political Aspects of Demographic Policy

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Abstract: This scientific paper presents the theoretical, scientific, and political aspects of demographic policy, why demographic policy determines the dynamics of the development of the country and the security of the state, and what the political aspects of demography are.

It is worth noting the fact that the United Nations recognizes demographic policy as a policy of policies. Demography - this is the dynamics of population development, both in terms of birth, death and other statistical data, as well as in terms of education, social and economic development. When the UN works on the development of demographic policy in any of its member states, representatives from health, economy, education, sports, youth and regional areas are involved in the working process. Since demographic policy reflects the dynamics of population development, it is often referred to as the main policy of the state. Most importantly, the growth and decline of the population, state borders, and aging of the nation are directly related to the issues of state security, therefore, countries with the most acute demographic problems establish the concept of state policy based on the very demographic policy.

In this specific scientific work, it is theoretically and factually justified why the demographic policy determines national security. It also discusses the demographic doctrines, the origin of demographic science and its main theories in detail. Moreover, it reviews the political aspects of demographic science and the reasons why demography determines state policy.

Key points: Demography, security, politics, state, doctrine.

Introduction

Attention to demographic science has been raised since demographic problems throughout the world have become more acute. Demographic data has become the main problem of the world since significant migration from developing countries to developed countries began. Initially, this fact was accepted as tolerance and democratic values by Western states. However, demographers and scientists from different countries of that period openly indicated the impending danger. Liberals considered these scientists to be neo-fascists and constantly criticized them. However, today, in just 20 years, both Europe and America have started to talk about the dangers of migration. Migration is considered to be one of the main demographic problems in the world today, especially in countries where the Aboriginal population is decreasing due to declining birth rates and is filled with migrants. Here we are already dealing with the change of ethno-culture. Over time, the state policy also changes in such states. That is why demographic problems are considered the main issue of national security.

The biggest threat to states expected from migration is demographic annexation. It is believed that demographic annexation is the most dangerous annexation in the world because the population

comes without any kind of war, peacefully and settles in your territory. If this population is excessive in terms of its ethnicity, over time it leads to a change in ethno-culture in the state, the emergence of its own representatives in politics, and most importantly, in most cases, the demand for ownership over specific territories. That is, a peaceful and seemingly humane act (receiving refugees) may turn into internal conflicts and war over time. There are many examples of this even from the recent history of the world, including in Georgia.

In addition to the fact that demographic policy is called the policy of policies, as a science it is recognized as a science of sciences. Demography as a science emerged at the end of the 19th century. Initially, it was considered that this science served only for the statistical description of the population, and over time, depending on the needs, it covered a wider area and today it reflects the depths of such sciences as medicine, sociology, economics, migration, regional development, etc.

When we talk about demographic policy, first of all, we should review demography as a science, its history and essence. According to the concise encyclopedic dictionary of demography, the term - demography is a Greek word and means "description of people".(Greek *dēmos* – people and *graphō* – I write), this is the science of the regularities of population reproduction. The term "demography" was introduced by the French scientist Achille Guiard in 1855. Demography, as a public science, to a large extent, studies demographic categories and laws¹.

The history of demography as a science begins in 1662. In this year, the English scientist John Grrfunt's first fundamental research on the problem of the population was published in London - "Natural and Political Observations based on Mortality Bulletins", and its scientific recognition began in 1882-83, after the holding of international congresses on hygiene and demography.

Researchers note that until the 70s of the XX century, the essence of this science was understood somewhat differently than today. It was mainly used as a synonym for population (demographic) statistics. With the research of demographers Avtandil Sulaberidze and Gogi Tsuladze, the system of scientific knowledge about the regularities of population development had mainly a descriptive character, since the 70s of the last century, the circle of research issues of this scientific discipline has been significantly filled, expanded and deepened. Today, it is no longer satisfied with obtaining actual data on birth rate, mortality rate, marriage, divorce, natural increase of population and other processes of a similar nature and describing and imagining the current situation².

According to demographer Gogi Tsuladze, demography developed so rapidly in the last period that it was fully formed and today, the system of demographic sciences is already in place. Together with the general theory of demography, it includes economic, historical, medical, sociological, ethnic, potential, ecological, regional, and descriptive provisions; The history of demographic doctrines, and demographic statistics. Probably, it is possible to outline new directions in the future.

Georgian demographers in the book "Fundamentals of Demography" provide us with a brief historical excursion about the term. According to their research, the term "demography" gained official recognition at the session of the International Congress of Hygiene and Demography in 1882: it was spread in the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

Originally, the term "demography" was used as a synonym for population statistics. In 1871, the German economist Ernst Engel proposed the term "demology" for scientists to describe this science. According to Engel, "demology" is the study of the internal nature and occurrence of variation in human entities in the state and other unions. Hrad opposition between demography and demology has not been established in science, however, in some cases the term "demology" is still used and an attempt to establish it has taken place recently. Academician Vazha Lortkipanidze's book "Demology" was recently published, where the scientist thoroughly explains why he uses this term.

¹ წულაძე გ.(2006). დემოგრაფიის მოკლე ენციკლოპედიური ლექსიკონი. გაერთიანებული ერების მოსახლეობის ფონდი: თბილისი. / Tsuladze G. (2006). Concise encyclopedic dictionary of demography. United Nations Population Fund: Tbilisi.

² ავთანდილ სულაბერიძე, გოგი წულაძე „დემოგრაფიის საფუძვლები“ (2006, თბილისი) / Avtandil Sulaberidze, Gogi Tsuladze - "Fundamentals of demography" (2006, Tbilisi)

In 1946, American sociologist Stuart Carter proposed another term - "demoscropy", which refers to obtaining information about the population by various methods. In addition to demography, demology and demoscropy, we find another term - "demometrics", which implies the measurement of demographic processes, that is, the use of mathematical methods in demography. The term was proposed by the Swedish scientist Hannes Hurenius as a synonym for mathematical demography.³

Even though information about the population was known from ancient times, it is believed that the first scientific and theoretical demographic work - "Introduction" - about the population was written by Ibn Khaldun in 1377. However, the scientific research on the regularities of population development still mainly takes its beginning in the 17th century, and the English scientist John Graunt is considered to be its founder, under whose authorship 10 works were published in 1662 "Natural and Political Observations based on the mortality bulletins". John Graunt studied data on deaths and births in London for an 80-year period and identified certain patterns for the population. He found that boys are born more than girls. He also found that among the dead there were more men than women. John Graunt also determined that the number of the population can be determined based on the number of births and deaths. According to him, based on the age structure of the deceased, it was possible to determine the age structure of the population.

The contribution of the famous scientist Edmund Halley to the formation of demography as a science is important. In 1693, he was the first to build a complete table of mortality. The works of Thomas Malthus, who worked at the end of the 18th century and the beginning of the 19th century, are also worth mentioning. His views are based on the opinions of the political, social and economic sciences of that time. In 1798, his work "Experience of the Law of Population concerning the future perfection of society" was published. Thomas Malthus emphasized the determining role of biological factors in population reproduction and believed that due to biological characteristics, the population grows much faster rather than due to the means of existence. The scientist believed that in order to regulate the ratio between the number of the population and the number of means of production, it is necessary to reduce the population. In his opinion, in the absence of overpopulation, the main reason that caused the plans of conquest, and tyranny and indignation inside the country -, would be eliminated. Malthus' population theory was interdisciplinary in nature and included demography as well as philosophy, political economy and political science. Malthus' views had a significant impact on the 19th and 20th centuries. on the development of public sciences.

In the middle of the 20th century, scientists found that demography cannot be reduced to the statistics of natural population movement and migration, demography has a specific subject of its research, a certain side of reality, which is not studied by any other science.

In particular, the renewal of the human generation, i.e., the correlation between the formation of the structure of the birthrate and mortality, sex and age of the population, as well as the processes of marriage and divorce, which belongs to the reproduction of the population as a whole **(G. Tsuladze, A. Sulaberidze "Fundamentals of Demography", Tbilisi 2015, p. 10)**

Demography is closely connected to other sciences because it uses the knowledge and experience of other sciences. Scientists explain its interdisciplinary nature as follows:

"Consideration of population reproduction as a process determines its connection with historical science. The connection of demography with economic sciences stems from the influence of the level of development of productive forces and economic factors on demographic processes. The dependence of population reproduction on social institutions and social relations determines its connection with sociology. The study of types of demographic behavior determines the relationship between demography and psychology. Some demographic cases are regulated by legal norms, and demographic policy is reinforced by legislation, which indicates the connection of demography with jurisprudence. Settlement of people and their movement affects population reproduction. At the same time, demographic processes are ongoing and discussed among the residents of a certain area.

This determines the relationship between demography and geographical science. Demography is related to medicine, biology and other sciences. It is worth noting the connection between

³ (გ.წულაძე, ა.სულაბერიძე „დემოგრაფიის საფუძვლები“, თბილისი 2015, გვ.10) / (G. Tsuladze, A. Sulaberidze "Fundamentals of demography", Tbilisi 2015, p. 10)

demography and mathematics. Therefore, demography is an interdisciplinary science and mainly focuses on birth and mortality.⁴

By the beginning of the 21st century, demography was taught in more than 300 universities around the world, and dozens of demography textbooks were published. Among them, many demographic works are published in Georgia every year.

Demography is closely related to adjacent sciences: economic theory, sociology, history, geography, statistics, ethnology, as well as several natural sciences. Several doctrines have been developed in demography. Let's review the main ones:

Ryder wrote in 1964 that "a population is a unity of individuals within a spatial and temporal development. According to him, there are two models of population development: microdynamic (individual) and macrodynamic (total).

Lotka (1934) explained the difference between the micro and macrodynamic development of the population as follows: "Individuals die, and the population as a whole continues to exist."⁵

Pre-modernist period scientist Genesis (1300) formulated his own thesis: "Be fertile and multiply and fill the earth."

Confucius (-500 AD) believed that governments should maintain a balance between population and natural resources. For Plato, the quality of the population was much more important than its quantity (-360); Aristotle considered abortions permissible based on the view that the population should be limited (-340); Cicero, on the contrary, considered population growth as a necessary condition to preserve the Roman Empire (50);

Later, already in the 14th century, Ibn Khaldun proved scientifically that with the growth of the population, professional specialization grew, which gave rise to incomes. Therefore, he considered the growth of the population as positive and inevitable. The same doctrine was formulated by other scientists, especially the followers of mercantilism, who noted that population growth increased trade and economic development between countries.⁶

Malthus's theory is well-known among the modern demographic doctrines, according to which the world could not withstand population growth because there were no resources: "Poverty is the result of the lack of moral restraint."⁷

Neo-Malthusians advanced the same theory. According to them, it was necessary to introduce birth control mechanisms that would control population growth accordingly.

In 1844, Marxians (followers of Karl Max's teachings) formulated a completely different doctrine: - "Each country has its own law of population development, which determines the consequences of population growth." Marxians opposed the theory of Malthus and opposed capitalist approaches with socialist views. For them, the increase in birth rate was a necessary condition for the development of the country.

Since the middle of the 20th century, the original form of the theory of demographic transformation of the population was formed. According to this theory, demographic transition is the process when a country moves from high birth and death rates to low birth and death rates.

Soon, scientists felt that it was necessary to reform the theory of demographic transition. And since the 1970s, the theory of demographic transition has been divided into its individual topics: reproductive health, birth and mortality, family policy, aging, migration, urban development, and the household. (8-9) Scientists have formulated separate theories on each topic.⁸

Even though demographic science has been divided into several areas and relevant theories have been created, in general, 4 theories are distinguished in demography: the Malthusian theory, the theory of zero population growth, the theory of cornicopia and the theory of demographic transition.

⁴ (გ.წულაძე, ა.სულაბერიძე „დემოგრაფიის საფუძვლები“, თბილისი 2015, გვ.29) / (G. Tsuladze, A. Sulaberidze "Fundamentals of demography", Tbilisi 2015, p. 10)

⁵ Theories of demography Ernesto F. L. Amaral September 3–7, 2018 Population and Society (SOCl 312) 3

⁶ Theories of demography Ernesto F. L. Amaral September 3–7, 2018 Population and Society (SOCl 312) 5–6

⁷ Theories of demography Ernesto F. L. Amaral September 3–7, 2018 Population and Society (SOCl 312) p.7

⁸ (Theories of demography Ernesto F. L. Amaral September 3–7, 2018 Population and Society (SOCl 312) p.10)

Malthusian theory

Thomas Malthus (1766-1834) was an English clergyman who made dire predictions about the possibilities of the earth. According to Malthusian theory, population is controlled by three factors: war, famine, and disease, which increase death rates. According to his opinion, the population of the earth is excessive and the resources of the earth are not enough for them.

Malthus observed and was surprised by the fact that the socio-economic situation was not improving, the number of the population was increasing. He was convinced that eventually population decline would be inevitable given the depletion of food, frequent wars, epidemics, and other conditions. It is worth noting the fact that Malthus worked in the 18th and 19th centuries.

The predictions of Thomas Malthus did not come true. The world's population continued to grow. Increasing the amount of calories in food production and the development of medicine led to a decrease in mortality and a gradual increase in life expectancy. Scientists predict that the population of the planet will increase even more. However, some researchers still believe that the Malthusian theory was true and that the Earth will run out of resources for its population.

Zero population growth theory

Neo-Malthusian scholar Paul Ehrlich revised Malthusian predictions in the twentieth century. According to Ehrlich's research, food will play an important role in the health of the planet's population due to a polluted environment, as privileged people use the environment and influence its pollution, water and air.

He supported the theory of zero population growth. According to this theory, the population by birth or immigration is equal to the population by death or emigration. The theory of zero population growth is supported by some scientists and is still considered a possible solution to global overpopulation.

Cornucopian theory

Some theories are less focused on the pessimistic hypothesis that the world's population will arbitrarily reach annihilation. The cornucopian theory makes a mockery of the idea that humans can self-destruct, that is, the population to cease to exist. It also argues that human ingenuity can solve any environmental or social issues that arise in the world. For example, if the population needs more food, agricultural science has advanced enough that they can feed the population and provide them with food. With all this in mind, followers of the cornucopian theory affirm that human ingenuity will bring about beneficial changes to the world and there is no reason why the population should cease to exist.

Demographic transition theory

According to the theory of demographic transition, future population growth will take place in four predictable stages:

1. In the first stage, birth, death, and infant mortality rates are all high, and life expectancy is short. An example of this stage is the 1800s in the United States of America.
2. As countries begin to industrialize, they enter the second stage, where birth rates are high and mortality and infant mortality are falling. Life expectancy also increases. An example of this is currently Afghanistan.
3. In the third stage, the society is well industrialized. The birth rate is declining, although life expectancy continues to increase, the death rate is decreasing. An example of this is the population of Mexico.
4. The fourth stage is the post-industrial era of society, birth and mortality rates are low, people are healthy and live long. The population is entering a stable phase, however, the total population may be declining. An example of this is the population of Sweden.

The United Nations Population Fund (2008) classifies nations as having high fertility, medium fertility, or low fertility. According to United Nations studies, rapid population growth is expected from 2011 to 2,100 in high-fertility countries, currently concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa.

For countries with average fertility (the United States, India, and Mexico), population growth is about 26 percent.

And in low-fertility countries like China, Australia, and most of Europe, the population actually declines by about 20 percent. The graphs below illustrate this trend (tables).

The first demographic manual in Georgia was issued in 1955 ("Demographic Statistics") under the supervision of G.Gamkrelidze. In 1986, the lecture course "Population statistics based on the basics of demography" was published by M. Khmaladze. V. Borisov's textbook Demography translated from Russian into Georgian, and published by A. Sakhvadze in 2001, is interesting. The "Concise Encyclopedic Dictionary of Demography" compiled by G.Tsuladze is also very important; M. Selia's lecture material "Population Economics and Demography". In 2007, the textbook - Demography compiled by G.Tsuladze, N.Maglaperidze and A.Sulaberidze was published. A. Totadze's works are important, including "Demographic Development of the Population of Georgia", G. Meladze's "Demographic Winter of Georgia", V. Lortkipanidze's "Demology" and others.

Academician Vazha Lortkipanidze believes that demographic policy is a part of "population policy" and, in turn, represents one of the most important parts, components of social policy: - "Demological policy is the targeted activity of the state and other social institutions in the sphere of the population reproduction process and the regulation of demographic events. It includes a system of goals and means of achieving them. As a rule, demographic policies are formulated and implemented based on long-term interests. Demographic policy is a set of economic, legal, educational, propaganda measures, the purpose of which is to form relevant public opinion and standards of demographic behavior and create a certain demographic climate in society.⁹ Let's get acquainted with the history of the demographic development of Georgia and its political aspects.

At the modern stage, the main subject of scientific research of Georgian demographers is the acute demographic situation in Georgia. Currently, Georgia is one of the few states in the world that are facing a real demographic threat. In Georgian demographic science, a lot of interesting studies have been conducted in all directions, which deeply reflect the demographic situation in Georgia and the expected serious threats.

There is a local office of the United Nations Population Fund in Georgia, which, with its large-scale research, helps the government of the country to correctly conduct its demographic policy. In 2010, the United Nations Population Fund published the results of a demographic study conducted by foreign researchers in Georgia, according to which Georgia faces a demographic catastrophe by 2050. The population of the country is decreasing by 28%, that is, by 1,700,000 people. While in the neighboring states, the population of Azerbaijan is growing by 33%, and the population of Armenia is growing by 7%. In the Caucasus, the demographic balance is being disturbed, which is directly related to the change in interstate politics. The demographic balance is violated only at the expense of the decrease in the population of Georgia. In such a case, Georgia loses its role as a dominant state in the Caucasus.

The United Nations Population Fund conducted several studies in Georgia in 2010, 2014, 2015 and 2017 with the participation of international experts. Studies have looked at the causes and expected consequences of demographic problems. Also, the United Nations Population Fund offered a complete analysis of the 2014 population census of Georgia, in terms of birth rate, mortality, migration, reproductive health, aging, and more. As a result of the research, the UN Regional Office has prepared recommendations for the Georgian authorities, where the main emphasis is placed on problematic issues, expected threats and changes in state policy over the next decades.

In order to be sure why the demographic policy is the beginning of the state policy, it is necessary to get acquainted with the demographic history of Georgia. With this review, we will be convinced that the strength of the state follows the size of the population. The country was strong in those years when it had a large population.

Among the Georgian demographers, the famous demographer Anzor Totadze conducted in-depth historical-demographic studies. He published several books not only about the demographic

⁹ (ვ. ლორთქიფანიძე დემოლოგია, 351 გვ. თბილისი 2018) / (V. Lortkipanidze Demology, 351 p. Tbilisi 2018)

data of Georgia but also about the demographic indicators of individual regions. According to his research, information about the population of Georgia in the early centuries before Christ is not available, but from the ancient written sources that have reached us, it is known that innumerable Kartvelian tribes lived in some of its historical provinces.

According to A. Totadze's research, the population of Georgia was historically the most numerous in the first half of the 13th century. According to the census conducted in 1254, its population was equal to 8 million people. As a result of constant invasions, the population decreased to 761,000 by 1770. During this period, as a result of the spread of the Black Death, the population decreased further and reached 400,000. And then, by the end of the 19th century, the population of Georgia increased dramatically and exceeded 2 million.¹⁰

According to demographer Anzor Totadze, the Georgian nation faced the danger of physical collapse and extinction. It becomes more and more difficult to renew the same number of generations, which is much more dangerous than the significant slowing down of the process of spiritual continuity. Thus, the primacy of physical continuity is evident, for even a considerable decrease in the spiritual life of the nation can be overcome. Nations with a rich spiritual heritage, due to the situation of the times, in the case of the decline and almost cessation of their cultural life, still manage to revive the cultural heritage, return and develop spirituality. This is determined not only by the nation's rich spiritual past but also by the fact that the nation's gene pool is the carrier of this rich spirituality.

When we talk about demography as one of the important components of national security, it is important to know what areas this science covers. The most important and most essential thing in this regard is birth. Continuous fertility research is one of the main components of demographic science. Anzor Totadze's study "Demographic Situation of Georgia" describes in detail the dynamics of birth in Georgia. According to this study, the most children were born in Georgia in 1961 - 104 thousand. Between 1960 and 1990, an average of 93,000 children were born every year. A sharp decrease in the birth rate began in 1992. In 2005, 46,000 children were born in Georgia, and the birth rate decreased by 2 times compared to previous years. Mainly as a result of this, in recent years, the natural increase in the number of population has also decreased significantly. Even during the 2nd World War, in particular in the years 1941-1945, the natural increase was 135 thousand people, while in 2002-2006 this figure was equal to only 5.8 thousand people. The fact that in the South Caucasus, where indigenous peoples -Georgians, Armenians and Azerbaijanis live, the demographic development of Georgians is substantially different from the demographic development of Armenians and Azerbaijanis is very significant. At the same time, it should be considered that the South Caucasus is one entire region, where natural and climatic conditions and the general lifestyle are somewhat close to each other¹¹.

Thus, modern birth parameters are almost twice as small as what is needed for generational replacement. When a woman gives birth to 1.3 children in her lifetime (in some years these figures are much less) it can be said that she is actually substituting one parent. This process will manifest itself after 8-10 years and will reach its peak in the early 2020s if radical measures are not taken. In the case of an active demographic policy, which will be considered only for a long-term run, this process can be slowed down and the desired result will be achieved after a sufficient period of time.

The well-known demographer Anzor Sakhvadze has also conducted studies on birth and mortality rates. According to him, the mortality rate in Georgia was traditionally low compared to neighboring and most European countries, but in recent years it has increased significantly. In particular, if 6.5 people died per 1000 people in 1960, this figure was equal to 11.3 in 2004. According to official statistics, the mortality rate has decreased sharply in 2017-2018.¹²

¹⁰ (თოთაძე ა. „საქართველოს დემოგრაფიული პორტრეტი“ თბილისი, 1993) / (Totadze A. "Demographic portrait of Georgia" Tbilisi, 1993)

¹¹ (თოთაძე ა. „საქართველოს დემოგრაფიული პორტრეტი“ თბილისი, 1993) / (Totadze A. "Demographic portrait of Georgia" Tbilisi, 1993)

¹² (სახვაძე ა. დემოგრაფიული ეტიუდები. თბილისი. 2005 წ.) / (Sakhvadze A. Demographic studies. Tbilisi. 2005)

Abortions are one of the main demographic problems. Georgia has always been distinguished by the number of abortions. According to official statistics, the number of abortions reached 40,000 by 2012, and the number of illegal abortions, according to experts, is much higher.

Abortions have increased among minors. Primary abortions lead to infertility in most cases. In general, infertility is a serious problem in Georgia. If before 2010 the seniority of infertility was 35 years, today it has reached 27 years.

As for abortions, selective abortions are important here, that is, as a result of sex selection in Georgia, in most cases, abortions were performed in favor of sons. Today selective abortions are prohibited in the country, however, it is very difficult to control.

Internal and external migration is one of the important demographic problems. Mainly due to economic circumstances. According to the data of the State Department of Statistics, 85% of those who left the country are of working age, while the share of this age population in the entire population does not exceed 2/5. The fact that gender inequality has been increasing in recent years makes the mentioned process especially dramatic. Among the young people who left Georgia, there are more women than men, which in the long run can cause serious socio-demographic problems.

According to official data, the first internal migration process in the country began in the 80s, when the rural population moved to cities to work in heavy industry. And then, since the 90s, due to the socio-economic situation, families closed their houses and moved to big cities, mainly the capital. According to demographers, a family that migrates cannot reproduce, because it is mainly focused on maintaining the family and settling in a new city.

The famous professor Leo Chikava notes in his research that if at the end of the 80s of the last century only one of the regions of Georgia - Racha-Lechkhumi-Kvemo Svaneti - experienced depopulation, today we have the same situation in five more regions - Guria, Imereti, Kakheti, Mtskheta-Mtianeti and Samegrelo-Zemo Svaneti.¹³

We are not doing well in other regions either. In the study of scientist Anzor Totadze, we read: "In 2012, compared to 1990, the natural increase of the population decreased 4 times in Kvemo Kartli, 11 times in Samtskhe-Javakheti, and there is almost nothing left to create a depopulation situation." The natural increase in rural areas in 2002-2014 amounted to 39,000 people. 495,000 people have migrated from the rural areas in the last 20 years. Some of them emigrated, some moved to big cities, where it seemed easier to make a living. When a person leaves the village, they lose their freedom and feel like a minority.¹⁴

Depopulation is especially notable in mountainous regions. According to the official data of the 2002 general population census of Georgia, 152 mountain villages were completely depopulated, while 10 or fewer people lived in 165 villages.

The 2014 general population census of Georgia has even worse data. At the moment, that is, according to the latest data, 202 villages in the mountainous regions of Georgia are completely depopulated, and 175 villages have 5 or fewer people, that is, they are half depopulated.

As for the border strip of Georgia, it is almost completely empty. However, the local population protects the border of the country better than the border guard. In this case, one infallible principle applies - if you move, others will settle, the signs of which are already visible in Georgia. This is the very demographic annexation, which begins with peaceful settlement and often ends with internal conflicts and loss of territories.

The demographic situation in Georgia, along with other circumstances, is significantly aggravated by the processes of emigration of the population (mainly young people). The number of people who have left Georgia has not been fully determined due to the difficulties of registration. Various expert calculations are negative and it reaches about one million, which is quite a large figure for a small country like Georgia.

¹³ (ჩიქავა ლ. „დემოგრაფიული კატეგორიები დაკანონები. თბილისი, 2002 წ.) / (Chikava L. "Demographic categories and laws. Tbilisi, 2002)

¹⁴ (თოთაძე ა. „დემოგრაფიული ვითარება საქართველოში და დემოგრაფიული განვითარების პროგრამა“. თბილისი, 2016) / (Totadze A. "Demographic situation in Georgia and demographic development program". Tbilisi, 2016)

Along with other negative processes, demographic aging of the population is going on intensively in Georgia. It has been considered a demographically aging country since the mid-70s. In the 1990s, due to the acute socio-economic crisis, the demographic aging process accelerated and the country reached a high level of demographic aging. According to scientific studies, the aging of the population means an increase in the share of elderly people in the population. The aging of the nation has become one of the most important demographic processes worldwide. According to the research of the scientist Mzia Selia, compared to many other countries, Georgia has already advanced significantly in the mentioned process, although it has not yet reached the final stage of this process. The results of the mentioned demographic event are already quite clearly visible in the country, although its full impact and the severity of the consequences, both at the individual and societal levels, are still not fully understood.¹⁵

The well-known demographer Gia Meladze has done comprehensive research on aging policy, which he published in the book "Demographic Winter in Georgia".¹⁶

According to G. Meladze, the process of demographic aging of the population belongs to a series of regular events. At the same time, it is one of the current socio-economic problems of modern times. Demographic aging of the population is defined as the percentage of the population aged 65 and over in the total population (in some cases, the share of the population aged 60 and over).

According to the research of not only Georgian but also foreign scientists, Georgia is a demographically aging country. The process of demographic aging was particularly intensive in 1992-1997, which was determined by two main reasons: a decrease of the birth rate at the level of simple reproduction of the population and the significant increase of emigration processes, where mainly the population under 60 years of age participated. Georgia is a specific demographic region, which is manifested in the peculiarity that in a country that is economically very detained, due to the sharp deformation of the age structure of the population, the level of old age of the population is significantly higher at 14% (2012). Among the 25 most demographically aging countries in the world, in 2008, Georgia was in the fourteenth place. According to today's data, Georgia is considered the most aging nation in Europe.¹⁷ Such indicators of the aging of the nation pose a serious threat to the economy of Georgia. When we talk about the importance of demographic policy in matters of national security, this is also what is meant.

As can be seen from scientific conclusions, the policy of demographic development of the population is directly related to the development of states, their existence and prospects. The doctrines of scientists about demography clearly reflect the circumstances of how important the number of people is considered in the process of survival of nation-states, including empires. It is also clear what role demographic policy plays in inter-state relations, the internal ethnopolitics of the country, and, in general, the stability of the country.

Today, the increased interest in demographic science at universities worldwide has proven the opinion that demographers substantiated with their research a century ago - demographic science would definitely become one of the leading and most important fields, the science of sciences, which would be used in the production of various policies.

From scientific theories and analysis of political documents, we can substantiate the hypothesis of our scientific paper:

Demographic policy is recognized by the United Nations as a policy of policies. If demographic policy is the basis of all policies, then it fully determines the security issues of the state. Especially when the development of states is directly related to the processes of natural population growth, migration and aging of the nation.

¹⁵ (შელია მ. „ხანდაზმული მოსახლეობა საქართველოში, სოციალური და ეკონომიკური პრობლემები“, თბილისი, 2013) / (Shelia M. "Elderly population in Georgia, social and economic problems", Tbilisi, 2013)

¹⁶ (მელაძე გ. დემოგრაფიული ზამთარი საქართველოში, თბილისი, 2014.) / (Meladze G. Demographic winter in Georgia, Tbilisi, 2014.)

¹⁷ (საქართველოს მოსახლეობის სტატისტიკური წელიწადი, თბილისი. 2009) / (Statistical Yearbook of the Population of Georgia, Tbilisi. 2009)

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